

MEDIATING ROLE OF E-WORD OF MOUTH ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VISUAL SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING AND CUSTOMER PURCHASE INTENTION IN JORDANIAN REAL ESTATE COMPANIES

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Abstract

This research examines the effect of visual social media marketing on customer purchase intention in Jordanian real estate companies while considering the mediating role of electronic word of mouth. Jordanian real estate companies are currently dealing with difficult marketing conditions and an environment that is becoming more competitive. A thorough study of the prior and current literature served as the foundation for the conceptual model of the investigation. The research model includes the visual social media marketing dimensions (informative content, entertainment content, and remunerative content) as independent variables that influence customers' purchase intentions as a dependent variable through electronic word of mouth as a mediating factor. The research uses descriptive and analytical techniques. To collect 300 questions disseminated via Google Forms, a convenience sample strategy was used. Received 225 replies. To analyze data and assess hypotheses, PLS was used in structural equation modeling (SEM). The findings of the hypothesis demonstrate a strong influence of visual social media marketing and electronic word of mouth on purchase intention. The association between visual social media marketing and purchase intention is mediated through electronic word of mouth. The findings offer Jordanian real estate companies' insights into the most effective ways to use visual social media marketing to entice customer to make purchases.

Keywords: visual social media marketing, purchase intention, electronic word of mouth, real estate, Jordan.

1. BACKGROUND

Jordan has demonstrated a favourable environment for real estate investment thanks to safety, political stability, and population growth of 2.4 percent annually, which increased demand for real estate. Investors who found lucrative opportunities in the Jordanian market and the country's large and growing young population also contributed to this favourable environment (Alheet et al., 2021, Alnsour, 2016). One of the most significant investments, both in Jordan and globally, is real estate (Khatib, 2020). Real estate companies have effectively employed all the marketing methods at their disposal because they want to sell houses as quickly as possible (Dumpe, 2015). When exhibiting and selling apartments, real estate agents emphasize emotional marketing to improve communication, quality, and create a favorable experience

with potential customers (Consoli, 2010). However, since the start of the COVID-19, investments in the real estate sector appear to be in a condition of deflation, and the marketing for real estate enterprises is difficult (Alrawashedh, 2021). Although Sales advertisements are rarely used by enterprises in Jordan's real estate sector (Al-Homoud et al., 2009). Dibs (2020) found that there was a positive correlation between marketing innovation in Jordanian real estate enterprise and its reputation and that real estate companies are thinking creatively about marketing their properties and striving for solutions that can increase market share and gain more profit. Even though sales advertisements are rarely used by businesses in Jordan's real estate sector. Real estate is one of the most important financial decisions you will ever make, so learning as much as you can about the apartment is necessary (Le-Hoang et al., 2020). One of the marketing channels that is frequently utilized to enable contact between producers, marketers, and customers or purchasers is social media. Less focus is placed on spoken content in advertisements and more attention is placed on graphics. Consumers' improved ability to recall visual processing is one factor in the change (Clow & Baack, 2018).

Consumers usually search for information uploaded by past customers before making purchases to feel more comfortable. It might spread through multimodal communications or electronic word of mouth (Yaseen & Jusoh, 2021). Additionally, customers can profit in several ways from connecting with brands on social media platforms. Viewers prefer communications with visual content since there is so much information available on social media, saving time and fostering more meaningful participation (Kujur & Singh, 2020). As a result, Jordanian social media users are influenced by other people's feedback, which can be shared in a variety of ways, including word of mouth, online reviews, and recommendations. As a result, Jordanian customers' purchase intentions on social media are influenced by factors like informativeness and entertainment. Al-Haddad and others (2012). Before buying any products, consumers trust eWOM; as a result, it significantly influences their purchasing intentions. Therefore, we also expect that if a product obtains favourable ratings from customers via eWOM, it will have an impact on other customers' purchasing intentions (Aji et al., 2020).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Background

2.1.1 Visual social media marketing (VSMM)

The concept of using video, photos, and other visual content (like infographics) to make your messages stand out from the noise and clutter and reach your audience more efficiently is known as visual social media marketing (VSMM). The most recent version of visual social media platforms categorizes them into three groups: photographs, videos, and live casting (Gretzel, 2017). Theoretically, social media are online platforms that let users or customers build semi-public profiles so they may interact with others and exchange ideas or experiences in a virtual environment (Kunja and Acharyulu, 2018).

More and more customers are using social media to find out about products or services (Ismail, 2017). Platforms for social media like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and YouTube are altering

how consumers connect with businesses and brands (Bianchi & Andrews, 2018). Visual content marketing uses images, videos, and infographics to share and present pertinent information to viewers (McMurray, 2021). Visual communication uses symbols and images to express ideas, and it can have an emotional or intellectual impact on viewers—or both at once (Hellberg, 2015).

Utilizing visual elements like as pictures, videos, infographics, and other visual elements is unquestionably more captivating and alluring to online viewers in general. Visual content will help you increase views, engagement, and social following in addition to helping your content attract the right kind of attention and encourage involvement from your target audience (Husman, 2017). According to Kujur & Singh (2020) the visual content of social media marketing contained three dimensions there are following:

2.1.1.1 Informative Content

Advertising that is informational has a beneficial impact on consumer attitudes, and a company's website's informational value directly affects how its target market views the business and its goods. Informative content is the ability to inform consumers of products so that purchases yielding the greatest possible satisfaction can be made (Hashim et al., 2018). Compared to plain text, visual content material conveys a lot more brand-related information to users swiftly and easily. Since they are more visually appealing, infographics, slideshows, videos, graphs, and charts can all be used to summarize information for social media users (Kujur & Singh, 2020).

2.1.1.2 Entertaining Content

The degree of pleasure and arousal that affects consumers' intents to use social media again and their desire to spread positive brand word (Dolan et al., 2016). According to Muhamad and Shahrom (2020), the entertainment content determines how pleasurable and enjoyable online media is for media consumers. Additionally, people may be drawn to interesting information that is regarded as exciting, enjoyable, cool, and occasionally amusing. According to Araujo et al. (2022) the potential of ads to deliver enjoyable and satisfactory entertainment.

2.1.1.3 Remunerative Content

Economic incentives like are monetary incentives, gaining direct discounts and coupons, accessing sales promotions, or personal wants (Buzeta et al., 2020). According to Muhamad and Shahrom (2020), the remunerative content refers to which social media provides financial or incentive benefits, delivers economic benefits, and attracts attention through social media offerings. Remunerative also refers to situations in which users use social media in the expectation of obtaining a reward, such as a cash reward, a professional benefit, or their own goals.

2.1.2 Purchase Intention

Purchase intention, which is correlated with consumer attitudes and preferences, is the prospect that a consumer will purchase a good or service in the future. Our conduct is influenced by intention (Alnsour et al., 2018). A consumer's decision to purchase goods or services because

they think they will satisfy their requirements and are compatible with their overall philosophy is referred to as having a purchase intention (Al-Adamat et al., 2020; Hammouriet al., 2021).

The first step toward rewarding actual purchasing behavior is thought to be purchase intent. Consumers' Purchase intention is a component of consumer cognition that reflects how a person is expected to purchase a specific brand (Pauzi et al., 2017; Ahmad et al., 2022). Like conventional purchasing procedures, social media's notion of purchase intent (Yaseen & Jusoh, 2021). Home ownership ambitions and actual purchasing behavior are increasingly closely related in the housing market. According to Karunarathne and Ariyawansa (2015), Intentions, or the conscious decision to exert effort to carry out a task, are what drive a person to take certain actions. These comprise the choice and purpose to purchase.

Particularly when it comes to acquiring a home, there is a significant association between the two stages. To put it another way, someone who has a strong passion for something is more likely to increase performance to complete the task at hand. Therefore, the definition of house purchase intention I is how keen clients are to purchase a home soon (Chia et al., 2016).

2.1.3 eWOM

Online word-of-mouth contact is known as electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM). This form of contact has grown into one of the considerable reliable bases of information on companies, goods, or trademarks because of the development of internet outlets (Huete-Alcocer, 2017). According to Cheung and Thadani (2012) Word-of-mouth media are far more trustworthy than traditional media (e.g., television, radio, print advertisements, etc.). Positive word-of-mouth marketing increases customers' intent to buy, but negative word-of-mouth marketing deters them from doing so, claim Baker et al. (2016). eWOM is a new term for online word-of-mouth communication (Electronic Word-of-Mouth) (Yang, 2017). The WOM, as defined by Litvin et al. (2008), is any unofficial internet communication directed to consumers that discusses the usage, features, or suppliers of certain goods and services. One advantage of using this technology is that everyone may share their ideas and opinions with other people by using internet platforms. Consumers now go to online reviews, or eWOM, rather than recommendations from friends and family when looking for information about a product or service (Nieto et al., 2014; Hammouri et al., 2021). eWOM does not have to be spoken or face-to-face; it may be communicated through multimedia communications (such as photographs, text, videos, audio, rankings, and ratings on the internet) and in aggregated or individual formats. (Pourfakhimi et al., 2020; Al-Gasawneh et al., 2022). Blogs, retail websites, discussion forums, and more lately social networking websites are all good places to look for the ideal eWOM platforms (Haibin, 2018). Word-of-mouth (WOM) via social media is the most reliable information source available on the Internet (Abubakar & Ilkan, 2016). It enables buyers to research brands and goods, make comparisons, and gain knowledge from the experiences of other users of a certain brand, good, or service before making a purchase (Park et al., 2021; Hammouri et al., 2022). Social networking websites are thought to make excellent eWOM platforms (Kim et al., 2014) Users can publish comments in the form of written text, photographs, videos, or even applications. Content that has been visually enhanced is more interesting and intriguing. Social media sites can make it easier to spread eWOM knowledge

to a big audience (Sohn, 2014). Social media has given eWOM a new dimension by allowing users to engage with their current networks. Social media, in contrast to other platforms, enables users to share their opinions and experiences with friends, acquaintances, and other individuals they already know (Erkan, 2016).

2.2. Hypothesis Development

2.2.1 Visual social media marketing and purchase intention

Research by Maria et al. (2019) set out to look at how social media marketing, word-of-mouth, and successful advertising affect brand awareness and the possibility that customers would make a purchase. The findings demonstrate that social media marketing and advertising effectiveness have a significant positive impact on purchase intention. Laksamana (2018) conducted a follow-up study to examine how social media marketing affects brand loyalty and purchase intentions. The findings demonstrate how social media marketing boosts brand loyalty and purchasing intent. In 2021, Wijayaa et al. completed another important study. This study looked at how social media marketing, trendiness, entertainment, engagement, personalization, and entertainment affected consumers' inclinations to buy smartphones. Each of these factors had an impact on purchasing intentions, according to the findings. The study by Sharifi and Yazdani (2022) and Ra'd Almestarihi et al. (2021) intends to explore how social identity, perceived value, and customer satisfaction in social media marketing activities affect consumer purchase intentions. The findings demonstrate that social media-based marketing initiatives have a favorable and significant influence on customer purchase intentions, purchase persistence and engagement. Research by Dewia et al. (2022) found that the fashion industry's use of social media marketing may have an impact on customers' inclination to buy. The study aimed to examine the relationship between social media marketing and brand awareness and how that relationship impacts purchase intention. Karpenka et al. conducted a study in 2021 to evaluate the effect of visual content on social media community groups. The results show that image-based content influences brand engagement with the content given by a brand inside social network community groups. Another study by Fox et al. (2019) examines how users' attention to the verbal component of user- and business-generated VSMM material, specifically on Snapchat, is affected by the usage of figurative language and Snapchat's drawing capability. The results show that the usage of figurative language and viewers' attention to the caption in user generated VSMM material may be influenced by the existence of graphical data in the content. According to a study by Argyris et al. (2021), which sought to understand how an influencer's extroversion functions as a personality antecedent to source credibility and purchase intentions, the visual representation of an influencer's extroversion increase the influencer's perceived credibility and, as a result, the influencer's purchase intentions. According to Shaouf et al. (2016), they examined the effects of the visual design of web advertising on consumers' tendency to purchase. The results show how brand attitudes and advertising attitudes in online advertising affect consumers' inclinations to buy. In their 2008 study, Kim and Lennon investigated how different methods of product presentation, such as verbal vs visual, impact customers' opinions of the goods and their propensity to make purchases when they shop online. Overall emotional and cognitive attitudes about clothing

goods were shown to be significantly influenced by both verbal and visual information, according to the findings. Aji et al.'s analysis (2020), this study aims to determine if social media marketing activity (SMMA) employed by brands and enterprises has a favorable effect on their brand equity, the propagation of eWOM on social media, and the purchase intentions of consumers. The outcome demonstrates how the SMMA has a direct impact on consumers' purchasing intentions. According to Majeed et al. (2021), the findings demonstrate that information and compensation have significant, favorable effects on brand equity as well as significant, favorable relationships between brand equity and customer purchase intention. The findings of a subsequent study by Moslehpour and associates (2021) revealed that the entertainment element of social media marketing had a significant, immediate effect on purchase intention. The results of research by Setiawan and Briliana (2021) showed that entertainment and informational value had a significant impact on purchase intentions. Hashim et al.'s (2018) study found that the entertaining and educational quality of the advertising message has an impact on how consumers perceive mobile phone ads. The chance of a consumer purchasing the advertised goods or services is correlated with attitudes about mobile advertising. Based on the previous studies the researcher developed the following hypothesis:

H1. VSMM has a positive impact on customer purchase intention.

2.2.2 VSMM marketing and eWOM

The study of Seo et al. (2020) state that the aim of this study was to explore the associations between social media usage traits and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), trust, and brand equity. Personality, social, and informational categories each contained one or more qualities. The findings demonstrate that social media usage's personality and informational traits had a statistically significant effect on eWOM. The purpose of the study, according to Dülkand Aydın (2020), is to examine how social media marketing affects consumer purchase intent, electronic word-of-mouth marketing, and brand loyalty. The results show that social media marketing has a favorable effect on eWOM and brand loyalty. Another research by Pramudhita and Madiawati (2021) investigates the potential benefits of social media marketing campaigns for eWOM and brand equity. The findings show that social media marketing campaigns have a positive and significant impact on eWOM. Based on the previous studies the researcher developed the following hypothesis:

H2. VSMM has a positive impact on eWOM.

2.2.3 eWOM and purchasing intention

According to a study by Park et al. (2021), Customers' intents to acquire luxury goods are positively impacted by social media WOM, demonstrating the significance of social media WOM in increasing luxury brand purchase intent. This study creates a theoretical model that clarifies how consumer participation in social media WOM, and luxury purchase intention are related to luxury perceptions. The results show that eWOM and customer perceptions of monetary value, hedonic value, and utilitarian value significantly increased purchase intention of ready-to-eat food, according to Sosanuy et al. (2021). This study examines whether electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) and customers' perceived value affect the purchase

intention of ready-to-eat food. a Nurittamont study (2021) The goal of this study was to ascertain how eWOM communication influenced working-age consumers' choices to purchase healthy food items. The results show that eWOM communication has an impact on working consumers' decisions to purchase goods, especially nutritious meals. In opposition to this, a study by Halim et al (2022), This study investigates how negative electronic word-of-mouth messages affect attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavior control, and the propensity to buy sustainably produced dairy products. According to the results, negative eWOM decreases attitudes, perceived behavior control, subjective norms, and buying intentions, with high negative eWOM decreasing purchase intentions more than low negative eWOM. Based on the previous studies the researcher developed the following hypothesis:

H3. eWOM has a positive impact on customer purchase intention.

2.2.4 eWOM as mediation

Research by Al-Gasawneha and Al-Adamat (2020) to assess the mediating function of eWOM regarding content marketing and its relationship with green purchasing intentions in Jordan found that eWOM had an impact on the correlation between content marketing and green purchasing intentions. Research by Purwianti and Khoviati (2021) the effect of service recovery characteristics, such as distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice, on patronage, with satisfaction and word-of-mouth (WOM) as a mediating variable in star hotels, was further investigated. The results show that WOM has been overrated as a mediating element between customer loyalty and satisfaction. Research by Rawal and Saavedra (2017), examined the impact of word-of-mouth on the movie theater business. Box office revenues and pre-release studio actions are thought to be mediated by word of mouth. The findings imply that word of mouth is the only factor mediating the connection between famous persons and box office receipts. Based on the previous studies the researcher developed the following hypothesis:

H4. eWOM mediator relationship between visual social media marketing and customer purchase intention.

3. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to examine how eWOM, a mediating factor, and influences the influence of visual social media marketing on customer purchase intention in Jordanian real estate companies. For this investigation, a quantitative descriptive approach built on a survey is deemed appropriate. The goal of this kind of research is to support an established theory that is relevant to current circumstances. The survey was conducted using a two-part questionnaire. The first section of the questionnaire included demographic data (gender, age, educational attainment, and income), while the second section included measurement of the study model components. The following sections of the questionnaire were used to evaluate each build: Informational content (4 items), entertainment content (4 items), and Remunerative Content (2 items) are indicated as the multi-dimensional variables to quantify visual communication in social media, according to Kujur and Singh (2020). According to Al-Gasawneha and Al-

Adamat (2020), eWOM only employed a unidimensional variable (5 items). According to Aji et al. (2020), purchasing intention was based on a unidimensional variable (4 items). To ensure reliable findings, the questionnaire contained 5 Likert scales.

4. SAMPLING

The population of the study includes every possible buyer of real estate in Jordan. In terms of sample size, the current study used the key informant methodology, selecting Jordanian residents who would be interested in buying real estate. At the same time, data was collected utilizing an online survey, employing tools like Google Forms. To select a representative sample of subjects or units from a population and gather sufficient relevant data from Jordanian real estate buyers, the study used non-probability convenience sampling. The sample size for this investigation was estimated using G-power statistical software, which used the following guidelines: F-statistical test, error probability to be 0.05 (which corresponds to a power level of $1 - \alpha = 0.95$), power standard to be 0.80, and multiple predictors to be 3 in this study (Alotaibi & Roussinov, 2016).

However, to guarantee that the required minimum of responses would be obtained and given that the survey method has a low response rate, the minimum number of respondents to analyze must also be greater than 100 questionnaires (Hair et al., 2010). To obtain more precise results, the study will distribute 300 questionnaires. Software known as PLS-SEM was employed to analyze the research data.

5. MODEL

6. RESULT

A total of 206 questionnaire items were used in this study out of the 225 that were brought back, 19 of which were excluded due to incompleteness.

CFA Model for Research Model

19 items altogether were used to measure 5 first-order constructs (IC, EC, RC, eWOM, CPI). The study used confirmatory factor analysis to evaluate the research model's measurement model. The measurement model is highlighted in figure 6.1

Figure 6.1: The measurement model

Convergent Validity

The confirmatory factor analysis for the measurements models as showed in Table 1

Table 1: CFA on the Research Model

Construct	Items	Factor loading	CR	AVE
IC	IC 1	0.910	0.928	0.721
	IC 2	0.896		
	IC 3	0.887		
	IC 4	0.881		
EC	EC 1	0.866	0.856	0.776
	EC 2	0.873		
	EC 3	0.877		
	EC 4	0.785		
RC	RC 1	0.883	0.843	0.783
	RC 2	0.881		
eWOM	eWOM 1	0.866	0.934	0.740
	EWOM2	0.874		
	eWOM 3	0.857		
	eWOM 4	0.888		
	eWOM 5	0.852		
CPI	GPI 1	0.884	0.891	0.622
	CPI 2	0.888		
	CPI 3	0.855		
	CPI 4	0.864		
VSMM	IC	0.955	0.912	0.743
	EC	0.908		
	RC	0.778		

The evaluation results of the model item's standardized factor loading are shown in table 1. The standardized factor loadings were all higher than 0.6, as can be seen (the loadings range from 0.778 to 0.995) as can also be seen, all constructs' AVE values ranged from 0.622 to 0.783. All these values exceeded cut-off value of 0.5 suggested by Hair et al (2010). Additionally, the composite reliability values ranged from 0.843 to 0.943 for all constructs, and these results all exceeded the suggested value of 0.7 for all constructs as in (Hair et al., 2010).

Discriminant validity

The current study obtained HTMT to measure the Discriminant validity for the model following to (Henseler, 2015).

Table 2: The HTMT for constructs

	IC	EC	RC	VSMM	eWOM	CPI
IC						
EC	0.633					
RC	0.733	0.739				
VSMM	0.763	0.743	0.761			
eWOM	0.843	0.654	0.799	0.543		
CPI	0.823	0.764	0.733	0.523	0.752	

All the HTMT values of the constructs, ranged from 0.633 to 0.843 were below 0.90, as can be seen in table 2. Thus, it demonstrates that each latent construct measurement was completely discriminatory with respect to one another (Henseler et al., 2015). The measurement scale used to evaluate the constructs and the item that make up each construct in the CFA model was valid and reliable, according to the analysis of the measurement model's convergent validity and discriminant validity.

Hypothesized Direct Effects of the Constructs in Structural Model

The hypothesis test and relationships in this section as shown in Figure 2, table 3.

Table 3: Hypothesized Direct Effects Structural Model

Path	St. β	St. d	R ²	Q ²	F ²	VIF	T-value	P-value
VSMM >CPI	0.497	0.144	0.442	0.341	0.220	1.720	3.451	0.000
eWOM>CPI	0.211	0.083			0.239	1.630	2.542	0.000
VSSM >eWOM	0.719	0,121	0.517		0.401	1.332	5.942	0.000

As seen in Table 3 the values of R² for CPI, eWOM was 0.442 and 0.517, respectively. This shows, for instance, that 51.7 percent of variations in eWOM is explained by its predictors (VSMM) and 44.2 percent of variations in CPI is explained by its predictors (VSMM, eWOM), proving that the R² values meet the criteria for the 0.19 cut off value as recommended by (Chin, 1998). According to (Chin, 2010), the values of Q² for CPI were 0.341, which are significantly greater than zero and indicate the model's high predictive relevance and acceptable fit. While the VIF values were 1.720, 1.630, 1.332, which were less than 5, (Hair et al., 2014). Additionally, the p-value of VSMM and eWOM in the prediction CPI were 0.000, 0.000 respectively, also in prediction eWOM the p-value of VSMM was 0.000. Accordingly, 0.01 and 0.05 are the probabilities of achieving through absolute p-value. Additionally, the path coefficient (St. β) values for (VSMM to GPI), (eWOM to CPI), and (VSMM to eWOM) were 0.497, 0.211, 0.719 respectively and this denotes relationships that are positive, thus all above discussion leading to support H1, H2 and H3.

Indirect effect of the constructs

The indirect relationship results in this section as shown in table 4.6

Table 4: Results of Hypotheses Testing for the Mediation

PATH SHAPE	St. β	St. d	T values	2.50%	97.50%	p-values
VSMM>eWOM>CPI	0.376	0.102	3.686	0.041	0.428	0.039

The result of Bootstrapping, as shown in table 5, showed that the indicated that effect VSMM on GPI through eWOM was positive and statistically significant at 0.05 level: $\beta = 0.376$, T-value = 3.686, P-value = 0.039. According to Preacher and Hayes (2004, 2008), the indirect effect Boot CI Bias Corrected did not straddle a zero in between, indicating that there would be a mediation effect (LL = 0.041, UL = 0.428). The finding showed that the mediation effect was statistically significant, which supported hypothesis H4.

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study put four theories to the test. The discussion of the effect of VSMM (informative content, entertainment content, and remuneration content) on customer purchase intention in Jordanian real estate companies constituted the study's initial objective. H1 was validated by the study, and the VSMM had a favorable, direct, and significant impact on purchase intention. This outcome is consistent with other research that suggested VSMM influences purchasing intention (Laksamana, 2018; Hashim et al., 2018; Kim & Lennon, 2008). This result suggests that VSMM customer purchase intention from Jordanian real estate companies. Customers are satisfied by VSMM when they interact with brands on social media. Due to the abundance of

information on social media, viewers prefer messages with visual content to save time and engage with the content efficiently. Additionally, visual content can inform buyers of items. The second goal, which was to research how visual social media marketing affected electronic word of mouth in Jordanian real estate enterprises, was represented by Hypothesis H2. The results of the investigation demonstrated that H2 was supported and that VSMM has a favorable effect on eWOM. This outcome is consistent with earlier research that suggested VSMM affects eWOM (Dülek& Aydin, 2020; Pramudhita & Madiawati, 2021). According to this finding, VSMM affects eWOM in Jordanian real estate companies. Through amusement and information, VSMM satisfies the customer and invites him to provide feedback. The third goal, which involved investigating how eWOM affected customer purchase intention in Jordanian real estate companies, was represented by Hypothesis H3. This theory was confirmed by the results, which indicated that eWOM positively affected purchase intention directly and significantly. This outcome is consistent with earlier research that suggested eWOM influences purchasing intention (Sosanuy et al., 2021; Nurittamont, 2021) According to this result, eWOM influences customer purchase intention in Jordanian real estate companies. Positive customer feedback on a product will influence future purchasing decisions. Before purchasing a good or service, people frequently read reviews left by previous customers since it makes them feel better. The fourth aim, which was to determine whether eWOM is a mediator between visual social media marketing and purchase intention in Jordanian real estate enterprises, was a final representation of H4. The findings suggested that the idea was correct. This outcome is consistent with earlier research, which showed that eWOM influences purchase intent and functions as a mediator in relationships (Al-Gasawneha & Al-Adamat, 2020; Purwianti & Khoviati, 2021). This demonstrates how eWOM improves and multiplies customer purchase intention via social media.

8. FUTURE RESEARCH

Few respondents provided comments to the survey, which was specifically focused on customer real estate companies in Jordan. As a result, future studies might want to carry out comparable research with a wider range of participants and examine the impact of VSMM on ROI (return on investment) and customer satisfaction in real estate firms in more detail.

This might help to clarify the mediation function of eWOM in the connection between VSMM and purchase intention. Future studies may also gain insight into the customers' viewpoint by looking at how VR (virtual reality) affects the likelihood of making a purchase. Future research may want to test the links suggested in this study to see if they apply to other nations, businesses, and industries. Because the study was cross-sectional in design, purchase intention and potential changes in the VSMM over time were not able to be recorded. The study also employed a quantitative strategy from the viewpoint of the user to accomplish its goals.

Therefore, longitudinal research studies could be conducted using another method, like a qualitative technique, to better understand the issues. These studies would help to comprehend the changes that might occur when VSMM dimensions are applied to purchase intention through a mediator. By acting as a mediator between them, this would serve to demonstrate

how a real estate company can properly conduct out VSMM and expose its impact on purchase intention. In this study, the association between VSMM and purchase intention was only partially explored. Therefore, it is advised that future research examines alternative mediators that could have an impact on the association.

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